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Correlation between Teachers' Capacity Building Programmes and Effective Service Delivery among Senior Secondary Schools in Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study focuses on correlation between teachers' capacity building programmes and effective service delivery among senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey. One research question and three hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consist of 1999 teachers in 57 schools in Abuja, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was used in selecting 323 teachers in accordance to sample size determination table. A researcher self-designed questionnaire tagged "Teachers' Capacity Building Programmes and Effective Service Delivery Questionnaire (TCBPESQ)" was used to collect data for the study. The instrument gave a reliability coefficient of 0.83. Descriptive statistics of percentage and mean score were used to answer research questions and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings among others revealed that is significant relationship between teachers' capacity building programme and service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Abuja. Based on the findings, the study concludes that teachers' attendance in capacity building programmes is a means of promoting school effectiveness. It therefore, recommended among other things that an evidence of capacity building programme should be considered as a major priority for promotion of teachers in public senior secondary schools.

Key words: Capacity building programme, school service delivery, instructional methods and classroom management

Introduction

Secondary education is known to be the link-bridge between foundation level of education (pre-primary and primary) and higher-level of education. It is a level of education that prepares students for higher institution of learning. The secondary education, as the name implies, is the second or next level of education in Nigeria system of education after the successful completion of basic or primary education. It is the programme of education the children receive between the ages of 12 and 18 years. It is the spring board from where all the students of higher education take of and all primary school leavers should undergo to be useful to themselves and society (Kaikai, Haruna, 2022). The value of secondary education in any nation of the world cannot be underrated. This is due to the fact that training for specific professional development is specifically and uniquely begins at secondary schools.

It is obvious that formalization of education programmes in Nigeria was introduced, practice and managed by missionaries as far back as 1882 before the government intervention in 1887. Ever since then, secondary education is not left out. This is an indication that among other levels of education, secondary education plays significant roles in human capacity development and nation building. The broad aims of secondary education as identify by Alabi (2022) are:

- i. preparation for useful living within the society, and
- ii. preparation for higher education.

The National Policy of Education (2013) sees senior secondary education as post-basic level of education and career development whose objective is to:

- i. provide holders of the basic education certificate with opportunity for education of higher level, irrespective of gender, social status, religious or ethnic background;
- ii. offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, disposition, opportunities and future roles;
- iii. provide trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grade; and

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iv. provide entrepreneurial, technical and vocational job-specific skills for self-reliance, and for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development, among others.

From the objectives set for secondary education in Nigeria and as laudable as those objectives are; the attainment of the set objectives could be a mirage if the teachers who are to interpret the contents of the curriculum and implement to have desired changes on students are lacking basic skills to withstand the dynamic nature of educational programme. Teachers are opening door for desired development in any nation but the teachers hold the key.

Teachers are important factor to be considered in ascertaining the goals of secondary education as far as senior secondary school is concerned. Teachers' roles towards ensuring the effectiveness of the school system cannot be over stressed. Therefore, their Job Performance such in areas like: record keeping, administration of discipline, school community relation, students' assessment among others are crucial to the effectiveness of secondary education. Teachers' job performance involves demonstration of competence and commitment to the process of performing the tasks given to them (Alabi, 2022). Teachers' activities are not hidden but are seen as factors that dictate the quality of the products as well as the quality of the schools.

Teaching as a profession is challenging in nature and this is as a result of diversified nature of the programme of education. The intricacies of the teaching job coupled with the demanding needs of the time have posed challenges to teachers. The premise that unless teachers provide effective instruction and create a conducive classroom environment to learning, students will not achieve at high levels, even when essential material inputs are available and the curriculum is relevant (Alabi, 2022). Teachers determine the happenings in the school. Most especially, the learning opportunity for the students is hanged on the quality of knowledge been possessed by the teachers.

Statement of the Problem

Researchers over the years have noticed that there is declining performance of students in secondary schools in Nigeria in terms of reading, writing, and practical skills (Omopariola, 2017). This is especially noticed among students in public schools. Some of the reasons accounted for this include the declining competence and commitment of teachers, inadequate provision of facilities, non-maintenance of available facilities, outdated and largely irrelevant curricula coupled with poor implementation. The aspect of teachers' incompetencies has been identified as inability of teachers to withstand the current dimension of educational system. That is, the global changes of teaching and learning (Ahmed, 2017). Teachers Without Borders (2006) as reported by Alabi (2022) stated that educational standard is measured from the products of schools. The cognitive and affective development of the students depend on the quality of the instructional delivery. Teachers controls classroom activities. Teachers create the love of continues learning for the students and they provide guide for future development of the students. For the teachers to be able to achieve all of these, such teachers must be updated in learning to be able to cope with new trend of relating with students.

However, building capacity of teachers should constitute school challenges of educational managers; bearing in mind that the manpower of any organization is its greatest asset. In the educational sector, teachers' capacity building has to do with updating teacher competencies for efficiency on the job. The process is made up of the sum total of learning experiences throughout teachers' career from initial training to retirement. These learning experiences ensure that the performance of teachers is high and contributes significantly in the accomplishment of educational goals. Researchers, such as Alabi (2023) and Ahmed (2017) see capacity building as a means of increasing teachers' knowledge, skills and competencies for effective job performance. Capacity building relates to human resource management in an organization, ensures that organizational members possess the new but relevant knowledge and skills needed to deliver effectively in their jobs, as well as take up new challenges, and adapt to changing environments.

Capacity is the ability to understand and do something while building is an increase in the amount of something over a period of time (Cambell, 2015). Hence, building capacity of teachers, for instance, is the conscious attempt at promoting, rebuilding, and gathering skills, abilities and strategies that must be promoted at regular interval to encourage teachers to contribute adequately to academic dynamics, as well as acquire professional training, effective teaching strategy and materials, effective skills for teaching, serve as effective role model, effectively enforce discipline and control of the students, enhanced condition of services, and the ability to ascertain the readiness of the students in the learning process. It is a process where teachers seize opportunity to gather new skills, ideas, attitudes or learning to promote the achievement of designed goals.

The purpose of capacity building programme is to improve an individual's skills or effectiveness in carrying out certain functions, solving problems, defining and achieving objectives. Thus, capacity building in education can be seen as a set of programmes designed to train or retrain teachers and other staff so that the learners would be able to benefit from the training. Capacity building programmes can be planned at two levels which include personal development and institutional development. A well-organized capacity building programme for teachers is believed to have influence on the quality of teaching and learning

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and in the long term, on students' learning outcomes. The focus of most capacity building programmes is on understanding the obstacles that frustrate or hinder people and organizations from achieving set goals and enhancing the abilities to achieve such goals.

World Bank (2011) describes capability building as the process of empowering the actors the society through learning, training, knowledge acquisition, information sharing and innovation to promote transformational and sustainable change in the organisation, which in turn promotes the achievement of the set developmental goals. Training is the act of transferring and taking information for the purpose of solving identified problems. This means that training is conducted to solve a particular problem. In the opinion of Agbatutu (2013) training is involving the development of abilities, skills and knowledge of the employee to carry out particular assignment to enhance productivity. Adeniji (2002) contended that training and retraining in educational system is geared towards work situation of an institution. This is because there may be situations where an institution has the required quality and quantity of workforce, yet experience low productivity; hence the need for more training and development in the institution. Effective training can have significant impact on the whole life of the worker in an organization and enhance productivity in the organization.

According to Stewart and Hart (2002), capacity building programmes classify approaches to teacher development under three general categories; thus: traditional, informal and intermediate approaches. The traditional approach refers to provisions made by the institution or the school system for improving the performances of school personnel from initial employment to retirement. Although, staff development generally recognizes that it is possible for teachers to improve their effective discussion activities. This approach is well suited to gathering routine information, updating teaching techniques and ideas relating to one's work.

Informal approaches involve the most innovative and provocative orientation to staff development in that they rely on exploration and discovery by teachers. Ferg (2005), in support of this, observed that informal approaches involve intense teacher's commitment, and the activities are initiated by teachers. Informal approaches are predicted upon the assumption that by providing teachers with an encouraging environment equipped with relevant teaching materials, media books and devices coupled with the generous encouragement of the employers, teachers will interact with this encouraging environment and with one another through research and findings. This approach encourages teachers to plan and work together. Teachers seek for help and new ideas from each other, thus strengthening their self-confidence and integrity. Intermediate approaches are essentially supervisory systems of staff development that result into cordial relationship without formal intervention. Teachers are exposed to logically structured programmes or activities through lectures, demonstration and observation to enhance their job efficiency and thereby leads to school effectiveness.

However, it is important at this juncture, to ask a very important question that how often is the attendance of secondary school teachers in capacity building programme? In an attempt to find answers to this question and other related to it makes this study to examine the relationship between teachers' capacity building programme attendance and effective service delivery in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The focus of this study is to examine the correlation between teachers' capacity building programmes and effective service delivery among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Identify how often teachers attend capacity building programmes among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria;
- ii. Examine the influence of teachers' attendance in capacity building programme on the use of instructional method among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria;
- iii. Determine the influence of teachers' attendance in capacity building programme on classroom management among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria; and
- iv. Investigate the influence teachers' attendance in capacity building programme on teacher-student relations among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.

Research Question

One research question was raised to guide this study as follow.

How often does public senior secondary school teachers attend capacity building programmes?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building programme and service delivery among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria;

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Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ capacity building programme and use of instructional methods among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria; and

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ capacity building programme and classroom management among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is descriptive survey design. This is considered appropriate for the study because it gives account of the true picture of the observed variables without any manipulation. The population for the study covers all the public senior secondary schools in the six Local Government Area in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. As at the time of conducting this study, there were 57 senior secondary schools in the study area during the 2023/2024 academic session. There were 1999 senior secondary school teachers in all the 57 schools available in Abuja. A multi-stage sampling technique was used in selecting 323 teachers. The selection of 323 (175 females and 148 males) teachers. The selection of 323 teachers was guided by sample size calculator and Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table. Hence, total respondents chosen for the study 323. The research instrument used to collect data from the respondents was a research self-designed questionnaire titled “Teachers’ Attendance of Capacity Building Programme and School Effectiveness Questionnaire (TACBPSEQ)” and its content and construct validation were observed before been subjected for reliability test. A 0.83 score obtained for reliability study and this shows that the instrument is reliable. Descriptive statistics of percentage and mean score were used to answer research question and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The mean score is used to take decision as follows:

Table 1

Decision Making for Descriptive Analysis

Mean Score	Decision
3.00 - 4.00	Very Good
2.00 – 2.99	Fair
1.99 - 0.00	Poor

Presentation of Results

Research Question

Research Question: How often does public senior secondary school teachers attend capacity building programmes?

Table 2

Analysis of Teachers’ Attendance in Capacity Building Programmes in Abuja Public Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria between year 2021 and 2023

S/No	Items	No & (%) of time attended				Mean Score	Decision
		None	One time	Two times	Three times		
1	2021	250 (77)	73 (23)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1.45	Poor
2	2022	211(65)	70 (22)	42 (13)	0 (0)	2.11	Fair
3	2023	237 (73)	80 (25)	6 (2)	0 (0)	2.21	Fair
Composite Mean						1.92	Poor

Source: Field report, 2023

Table 2 presents the analysis of teachers’ attendance in capacity building programmes among teachers in public secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria between year 2021 and 2023. The mean scores teachers’ attendance in the capacity building programmes were rated 1.45, 2.11 and 2.11 respectively and composite mean score was 1.92 and this is rated poor. The implication of this result is that majority of the teachers in the study area are not privilege to attend any of the capacity building programmes within the year frame. The implication of this is that teachers in the study schools were eroded to be updated on the new trends for their professional development. It is on this account, Alabi (2023) and Otu (2020) argued that capacity building programmes for teachers are means of increasing teachers’ knowledge, skills and competencies for effective

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job performance. Teaching as a profession is a dynamic job which is characterized by frequent changes. And, for teachers to move along with changing nature of teaching profession; there is need for update skills and knowledge through training and retraining. Modern system of education demands high quality teaching and learning from teachers that possess a great deal of knowledge and skills with regard to both teaching and assessment practices in order to meet those demands and standards of quality education. Twenty-first century education is about skills –sets of processes. Our students need to be able to adapt to contexts, meet challenges, and solve problems that are as yet unknown. Training is teaching, or developing in oneself or other's any skills and knowledge that relate to specific useful competencies. Training has specific goals of improving one's capability, capacity, productivity and performance. Training constitutes a basic concept in human resource development. It is concerned with developing a particular skill to a desired standard by instruction and practice. Training is a highly useful tool that can bring an individual into a position where they can do their job correctly, effectively, and conscientiously.

Research Hypotheses

Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1: *There is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building programme and service delivery among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria*

Table 3

Testing of the Relationship between Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building programme and School Effectiveness in Abuja Public Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria

Variables	No	Mean	Standard Deviation	Df	p-value	r-value	Decision
Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building Programme	323	3.45	2.01	321	0.01	0.73	Rejected
School Effectiveness	323	3.11	1.78				

Tested @ 0.05 level of significance.

Source: Field report, 2023

The testing of the relationship between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and school effectiveness in Abuja public senior secondary school, Nigeria is presented in Table 3. The calculated r-value is 0.73 and p-value is 0.01. Thus, the significance level is 0.05. Hence, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. This shows that the null hypothesis saying there is no significant relationship is hereby rejected. It means that positive and strong (0.73) significant relationship is found between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and school effectiveness in Abuja public senior secondary school (cal. $r = 0.73$; p -value of $0.01 < 0.05$ significance).

Hypothesis 2: *There is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building programme and use of instructional methods among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria*

Table 4

Testing of the Relationship between Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building programme and Use of Instructional Methods in Abuja Public Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria

Variables	No	Mean	Standard Deviation	Df	p-value	r-value	Decision
Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building Programme	323	2.63	0.98	321	0.01	0.68	Rejected
	323	2.13	0.52				

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Use of
Instructional
Methods

Tested @ 0.05 level of significance.

Source: Field report, 2023

As shown in Table 4, the test for relationship between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and use of instructional method in Abuja public senior secondary schools, Nigeria. The calculated r-value is 0.68, the p-value is 0.01 and the level of significance is 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis saying that there is no significant relationship between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and use of instructional methods is hereby rejected. This implies that positive significant relationship is existing between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and use of instructional methods.

Hypothesis 3: *There is no significant relationship between teachers' capacity building programme and classroom management among public senior secondary schools in Abuja, Nigeria*

Table 5

Testing of the Relationship between Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building programme and Classroom Management in Abuja Public Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria

Variables	No	Mean	Standard Deviation	Df	p-value	r-value	Decision
Teachers' Attendance in Capacity Building Programme	323	3.05	1.07	321	0.00	0.64	Rejected
Classroom Management	323	2.01	1.12				

Tested @ 0.05 level of significance.

Source: Field report, 2023

As indicated in Table 5, the calculated r-value is 0.64 and p-value is 0.00 while the level of significance is 0.05. This shows that the null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and classroom management in Abuja public senior secondary schools, Nigeria is hereby rejected. This means that positive and significant relationship is existing between teachers' attendance in capacity building programme and classroom management in the study area (cal. $r = 0.64$; p-value of $0.01 < 0.05$ significance).

Discussion of Findings

The roles of teachers are undeniable when it comes to goal achievement of education programmes in any nation of the world. As previously observed that if education is an opening door for national development as anticipated in the National Policy on Education (2013), then teachers hold the key. This is why it is imperative to always keep teachers on the tones or ensure that they work in right direction by doing the right things regardless of the dynamic nature of the programme of education. In this study, effort is made to identify capacity building programmes as one of the key factors for improving the quality of teachers for professional competencies. Although, and as presented in Table 2 of this study, poor attendance of teachers in capacity building programmes is recorded in the study area with composite mean score of 1.92. This is why public senior secondary is identified with old style of professional discharge. In the sample schools, the sitting arrangement of students in classroom is not learned centred. Mostly, teachers are used to lecturing method of teaching and many more old teaching acts that cannot withstand the 21st century system of education. There is need to keep teachers updated in terms of new knowledge, principles and skills. Students stand to gain more from teachers' updated knowledge. According to Omopariola (2017), teachers stand to do their best in their professional discharge if only they possess new skills and knowledge. This what the teacher stands to benefit in their attendance in capacity building programme.

Meanwhile, positive significant relation existed between teachers' attendance in capacity building programmes and teachers' job performance in Abuja public senior secondary schools, Nigeria. This implies that the best of teachers can do has to with learning opportunities received in their attendance in conferences, workshops and seminars. Training and retraining of

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teachers as described by Ayodimeji (2015) as vital and sensitive education activities to rebrand teachers and other key players of educational industry. Teachers should approach capacity building workshops with much interest hoping to benefit from it. With the knowledge gained teachers, they will be in a better position to impart knowledge, positive attitudes, skills to the students and the community at large. Often when new schemes are launched in our education system, teacher development is an important aspect of a practicing teacher, it involves the teacher's participation in short period refresher courses, in-service training, seminars, workshops, part-time evening programmes, the development programme is needed in order to keep the practicing teacher abreast with new knowledge, ideas, concepts, values and needs of the society, more also rapid trend in the wave of technological changes, is an added impetus to the need to retrain our teachers who are supposed to impart these new values to the younger generation.

The results of the operational hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance revealed that there is positive relationship or influence between teacher attendance in capacity building programmes and use of instructional methods and classroom management as p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance (p-value of $0.01 < 0.05$ sig. and p-value of $0.00 < 0.05$ sig). These results indicated that teachers' ability and efforts towards the use of instructional methods and classroom management will not just improve but will be blended to cope with the contemporary trends of educational system. Ayodimeji (2015) observed that curriculum of education can only be best translated and used to benefit students only when teachers are in vogue with current circumstances of imparting knowledge in the 21st century.

Conclusion

The art and science of teaching profession is guided by the established principles and ethics. These principles and ethics are subject to change as changes reflect in the life of man and the society to which the programme of education tend to serve. It is a must for teachers to understand the circumstances that surrounded the changing nature of their profession and seek knowledge and skills to cope with the challenges change might cost. Teaching among other profession of man is complex and dynamic. This is the reason why researching to seek for new knowledge by teachers becomes mandatory. Teachers are known for discovery in their respective areas of specialization. Capacity building programmes is an immediate solution to the current poor or unsatisfied teachers' performance in school and as well as keeping teachers abreast of social and educational changes. Hence, teachers' attendance in programmes like workshop, induction training, seminars and conferences should be encouraged by all education stakeholder to revive the lost glory of secondary education in public schools.

Recommendations

On the accounts of the findings in this study and the conclusion drawn, the followings are here by recommended:

1. The government and other stakeholders that are in-charge of managing public secondary schools should as matter of need attach importance to teachers' attendance in capacity building programmes so as to better the performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools;
2. Government and dedicated regulated body overseeing the affairs of public secondary schools should as matter of concern sponsor teachers to attend various capacity building programmes as regular interval;
3. As part of promotion requirements for teachers in public senior secondary schools; evidence of capacity building programme attendance should be considered as priority; and
4. Corporate and non-governmental organizations should be partner with in sponsoring teachers to attend capacity building programmes.

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